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**PROBLEMS OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN LEGAL EDUCATION
COVERAGE IN THE MATERIALS OF CONFERENCES AND
PERIODICALS OF UKRAINE**

The article reveals, systematises and analyzes scientific publications of Ukrainian scientists on the problems of legal education, highlights the statistics and dynamics over the years, generalizes the main tendencies of scientific direction development.

Key words: *public administration, legal education, legal literacy, scientific research, publishing activity, tendencies.*

В статті виявлено, систематизовано та проаналізовано наукові публікації українських учених із проблем правової освіти, висвітлено їх статистику і динаміку за роками, узагальнено основні тенденції розвитку наукового напрямку.

Ключові слова: *публічне управління, правова освіта, правове виховання, наукові дослідження, публікаційна активність, тенденції.*

Problem setting. To stimulate the development of science, it is necessary to support its information component, which ensures openness and dissemination of scientific knowledge in the scientific environment and popularization of scientific

research in the world. A wealth of scientific information, in addition to dissertations and monographs, also comprises scientific articles, reports and materials of scientific conferences.

A significant body of scientific publications on the study of the organization of law-education activity in Ukraine has been accumulated so far. However, the problem of assessing the scientific research results content remains relevant and essential for further development of this scientific trend.

Recent research and publications analysis. Various aspects of the national legal education system development are the subject of study of a large number of Ukrainian scholars (I. Alyeksyeyeva, B. Andrusyshyn, V. Vodnyk, S. Hladkyy, A. Huz, I. Ishchuk, O. Koval's'ka, O. Kostenko, D. Kumkov, N. Lyapunova, O. Mashkevs'kyy, B. Melekh, S. Nemchenko N. Onishchenko, O. Orlova, O. Plakhotnyk, I. Sopilko, N. Storchak, M. Trebin, V. Turyanytsya, H. Useinova, O. Fatkhutdinova, V. Cherevatyuk, V. Cherevatyuk, S. Shefel' and others). Some aspects of the organization and management of legal education and legal literacy are less researched in Ukrainian scholars' works (I. Vasyl'kivs'ka, A. Het'man, O. Danyl'yan, O. Dz'oban', O. Koval's'ka, V. Lozovoy and others).

The necessity of studying the state and trends of the Ukrainian scientists' publication activity indices on the problems of the organization and management of legal education, as well as the analysis of the scientific publications content of the conference materials and periodicals of Ukraine, conditioned the choice of research.

Paper objective. The purpose of the article is to reveal from the whole information flow of available scientific publications those highlighting the problems of organization and management of legal education; to determine quantitative indicators of scientific information, which make it possible to estimate the productivity of scientific activity of Ukrainian scientists towards this scientific direction; to analyse the content of scientific publications and narrow down the main trends in the scientific development of the problem.

Paper main body. In Ukraine, the transfer and assimilation of legal knowledge, skills and abilities are carried out in all educational institutions of the

state, mainly as a teaching of legal disciplines. However, in practice, legal education and legal literacy are often combined and are perceived as one of the directions of the educational process. Consequently, in the context of our study, it is expedient to consider publications that deal with both legal education and legal literacy. It is for these key concepts that the search of scientific works by Ukrainian authors was made, which resulted in 250 scientific publications (scientific articles, materials of scientific conferences) on the definite topic of research, of which 101 publications are devoted to legal education and 149 to legal literacy.

The results of the conducted research indicate that the number of scientific works of authors having more than one publication on the issues of legal education is 68, of which 32 are in pedagogics, which is the majority, namely 47,1 %, 15 – in philosophy, 11 – in history and 10 – in legal sciences. Among the authors who have the largest number of publications we can note the following: in philosophy – O. Fatkhutdinov (10); in pedagogics – L. Ryabovol (9); in history – A. Huz (9). Publications of only these three scientists make up 41,2 % of the total number of scientific papers on this topic. And these are only those scientific works that are available on the Internet-based network.

The total number of scientific works of authors having more than one publication on the issues of legal education is 137, of which the majority of works are represented in the legal sciences (64) and philosophy (53), which is 82,4 % of the total number of works in this direction. Only 20 works are presented in pedagogical science.

In general, the most scientific articles on legal issues are:

– in legal science – S. Maksymov (5), V. Zakharova (6), V. Trofymenko (9), which is 31,3 % of all scientific works in this science;

– in philosophy – S. Shefel' (5), O. Dz'oban' (6), O. Danyl'yan (7), Yu. Kalynovs'kyi (8), I. Kovalenko (10), which makes 67,9 % of all scientific works in this science;

– in pedagogics – O. Popadych (10) – 50 % of all scientific works in this science.

It can be argued that only O. Popadych is engaged in systematic research of the problem of legal education among the above-mentioned authors. In 2013 she defended her Ph.D. thesis on the topic "Pedagogical conditions of legal education of future specialists in the computer industry". In the work pedagogical conditions of legal education of future specialists in the computer industry were substantiated (development of the content of legal education on the basis of professional-oriented legal training; formation of value-legal orientations; enrichment of practical experience and development of legal skills as a prerequisite for legal behavior of future specialists of the computer industry); the structure of legal education was defined and its components were specified (professional legal awareness, professional legal development and readiness for legitimate professional activity in the computer industry), as well as criteria (cognitive-informational, value-oriented and professional-behavioral), indicators and levels of legal education for future computer specialists; the functional model of legal education of future specialists in the computer industry was developed and its effectiveness was experimentally tested in practice [11, p. 19-20]. According to the results of the research conducted by the scientist, 22 scientific papers were published, of which 8 were the articles published in the scientific professional editions, 10 papers were of approbatory character and 4 works, which additionally reflected the scientific results of the dissertation. However, unfortunately, not all of them are available on the Internet, which does not allow identifying the main ideas, provisions, and the results of scientific research.

Of all the masses of the discovered scientific works, only 10 publications address some aspects of the organization and management of legal education or legal literacy, of which 5 are scientific articles, and the other 5 are theses of the reports:

- Vasyl'kivs'ka I. Experience of organizing distance learning in the study of legal disciplines (theses, 2017) [1];
- Het'man A., Danyl'yan O. Experience of the legal education organizing in the system of secondary education of France (article, 2011) [2];
- Danyl'yan O. Some aspects of organization and management of legal education (theses, 2010) [3];

- Danyl'yan O. Experience of legal education organizing in the system of secondary education in Germany (article, 2015) [4];
- Danyl'yan O. Fundamentals of the organization and management of legal education (article, 2010) [5];
- Danyl'yan O. Features of the organization and management of legal education in a transitional society (article, 2012) [6];
- Danyl'yan O., Dz'oban' O. Features of organization and management of legal education in a democratic society (article, 2011) [7];
- Koval's'ka O. Information provision for the management of legal education of students in a secondary educational establishment (theses, 2010) [8];
- Koval's'ka O. The main tasks and directions of students' legal education management in the system of a secondary educational establishment (theses, 2009) [9];
- Lozovoy V. Some aspects of the legal education process management (theses, 2010) [10].

Only 6 authors deal with the issues of organization and management of legal education / legal literacy, four of them (A. Het'man, O. Danyl'yan, O. Dz'oban', V. Lozovoy) are teachers of Yaroslav the Wise National Law University, Doctors of Philosophy and Law. As can be seen from the listed scientific publications, the author of most of the works is Doctor of Philosophy O. Danyl'yan. It should be noted that the topics of his dissertation works are not related to legal education or its management (Candidate's thesis – "Contradictions in primary military units and the mechanism of their solution under the conditions of the Soviet society and the Army democratization" (1990), Doctoral thesis – "Social contradictions in post-totalitarian systems: the methodology of research and decision-making" (1998)). However, for the last two decades, the subject of a systematic study of a scientist has been the various aspects of legal education, including its organization and management.

Let us consider the content of the above mentioned scientific works in more detail in order to identify the main ideas and results obtained during their examination by the authors. Thus, his view on the organization and management of

legal education was put forth by O. Danyl'yan in his scientific works [3-7] (the latter is in co-authorship with O. Dz'oban'), which is as follows:

- the main stages of the organization of legal education are: analysis of the status of legal work in society and assessment of its effectiveness; development of current and long-term plans (programs) on the basis of this analysis; organization of practical implementation of the adopted plans (programs); social control over the effectiveness of legal work;

- an important place in the process of organizing legal work is occupied by: the legislative provision of legal education; activity of the state institution system represented by executive, legislative and judicial branches of power; coordination of state bodies and non-governmental organizations activities in the field of legal education; informational and methodological support of legal process; generalization and dissemination of positive experience in legal education, social control over the implementation of legal activities, etc.;

- the main areas of optimization of legal education in contemporary Ukraine are: the creation of a multi-stage system of legal education, which is devoted to ensure the continuity of legal educational actions concerning the population; raising the general citizens' morality; differentiated according to various social, professional and age characteristics of the population; promotion of legal knowledge, in particular, through mass media; awakening of the interest of the population to legal knowledge and ensuring their availability; advertising methods application; development of family legal education, etc.

O. Danyl'yan also argues that "for the organization of effective legal education in modern society, all legal actions must be combined into a system of interconnected, purposeful and consistent actions by various subjects of society, united by the general plan and following the only program" [7].

A significant contribution to the study of foreign experience in the organization of legal education in the system of secondary education was made by O. Danyl'yan and A. Het'man. Thus, in the scientific work "The Experience of Legal Education Organization in the System of Secondary Education in Germany", O. Danyl'yan

examines the history and experience of organizing legal education in the German system of secondary education, the specifics of conceptual foundations and the peculiarities of legal education, analyzes the basic legal values and the ways of their formation. In the conclusion the author notes that "the Ukrainian educational system needs to be reformed in the direction of increasing the hours for in-depth study of law, improving the general level of legal education of the younger generation, modeled on German education... The legal policy of the state should be implemented through legal education, legal advocacy and legal training" [4, c. 102]. France was elected as another foreign country to study the experience of organizing legal education by scientists A. Het'man and O. Danyl'yan. In the article "The Experience of Legal Education Organization in the French Secondary Education System" [2] the authors examine the specifics and peculiarities of the organization of legal education in each of the French secondary education cycles. An overview of the basic principles of the organization of both German and French legal education in the system of secondary education allowed scholars to conclude that legal education in the educational space of these countries is an integral part of the system of civil, legal and social education.

In his publication V. Lozovoy, considering some aspects of the management of the legal education process, concludes that this type of management involves identifying the educational opportunities of families, public organizations, cultural and educational institutions, and the media for the effective use of their influence on individuals, as well as the formation of traditions, propaganda of exemplary behavior, stimulation of the process of improving the legal culture [10, p. 241-242]. In addition, according to the author, the main task of legal education is the launch of the process of self-development, self-creation of a person with a high level of legal culture.

The final intellectual product of systematic research on legal issues organized at the Department of Philosophy at the Yaroslav the Wise National Law University, headed by O. Danyl'yan, is the textbook "Philosophy of Legal Education" (2012) [13] and the collective monograph "Legal Education in Modern Ukraine" (2013) [12]. The publication includes the scientific results that were previously highlighted in the

writings of scientists – the authors of these publications. The authors consider as the specific feature of the monograph and the course book their attempt to introduce legal education in the systemic dimension, while highlighting the theoretical and managerial aspects of this process. In particular, it is noted that in this context the basis of practical measures should be the dialectical unity of state and social activities aimed at maximizing the coordination of the functioning of the authorities, capacities and means of ensuring legal education activities.

The scientific works of O. Koval's'ka and I. Vasyl'kivs'ka actualize the generalization of the pedagogical aspects of the organization and management problems in legal education. In particular, in her works O. Koval's'ka [8; 9] considers the main tasks, directions and information provision of the legal education management process in secondary educational establishments. The author believes that to focus the attention of school principals on establishing a system of information provision of legal education management for schoolchildren in cooperation with all interested institutions and organizations will contribute to the effective solution of the problem of overcoming the legal nihilism of student youth and upbringing enlightened and law-abiding citizens of Ukraine.

Another scientist I. Vasilkivska examines the experience of organizing distance learning with the use of modern information and communication technologies developed at the State Higher Educational Institution "Vadym Het'man Kyiv National Economic University" in preparing students of different specialties, including future lawyers [1]. The author, demonstrating the benefits of distance learning, argues that due to this kind of study and student's self-organization his/her creative and intellectual potential increases considerably, a desire for knowledge arises, new opportunities in using modern information and communication technologies and the ability to make responsible decisions on their own emerge.

As a whole, the generalization of the existing base of scientific sources gives us grounds to assert that in contemporary scientific literature not enough attention is paid to the study of the problem of public administration in legal education in Ukraine. A significant number of authors consider only a few aspects of law

education subjects. In particular, the following aspects are considered in scientific works: the historical and theoretical foundations of legal education as a component of the educational system; formation of the content of legal education; the formation and development of legal education as a highly professional training of specialists; theoretical and methodological principles of legal training of pedagogical staff; legal education as a means of combating negative phenomena in society; the impact of legal education on the formation of legal culture and legal consciousness.

Conclusions of the research. In the end, we note that in the Ukrainian scientific environment a fairly large number of scientific works are presented, in which issues of legal education are highlighted. However, the publishing activity of Ukrainian scholars on the problem of public administration in legal education is very low in Ukraine. We found only 10 scientific publications which deal with some aspects of the organization and management of legal education or legal literacy. Practically all of them cover the practice (experience) of law-education activity organization. Consequently, in the future, more attention must be paid to the study of the theoretical foundations of the organization and management of legal education.

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